

Memorandum of Collaboration between

Rural BioReFarmeries & NUTRI-CHECK NET

This agreement is made between **Rural BioReFarmeries** and NUTRI-CHECK NET.

1. Purpose

The purpose of this Memorandum of Collaboration is to create the framework that will enable each partner to benefit from the common activities in their respective strategies. The present agreement is intended to serve as a guideline for both NUTRI-CHECK NET and **Rural BioReFarmeries** to enhance the relationship for the benefit of both partners, establishing the points and areas where both partners can meet interest developing a close coordination between the parties. This agreement will help both partners to pursue their respective goals and will help avoid any unnecessary duplication or inconsistency of work and publications.

Therefore, the partners agree that it is in their mutual interest to collaborate on specific activities aimed at facilitating and supporting cooperation, the exchange of knowledge and good practices as well as to partner up in the organisation of future events (online or in-person). The collaboration of both partners should enable each one to better achieve its respective objectives. Thus, NUTRI-CHECK NET and **Rural BioReFarmeries** agree to have a program of cooperation, which will include agreed actions and initiatives described in the following points.

2. Achievement of common goals

2.1. Meetings, events, and conferences

NUTRI-CHECK NET agrees to invite **Rural BioReFarmeries** to its meetings, events, and conferences, and **Rural BioReFarmeries** agrees to invite NUTRI-CHECK NET members to its meetings, events, and conferences. Both parties can provide collaboration in the organisation of national or international meetings, events, and conferences, collaborating with **Rural BioReFarmeries** and NUTRI-CHECK NET.

2.2. Projects, development, and support

Rural BioReFarmeries and NUTRI-CHECK NET agree to collaborate in the creation and implementation of projects for their mutual benefit. This is aimed to enhance their respective impact on issues and topics where both partners have common interest.

2.3. Communication and renown

Rural BioReFarmeries and NUTRI-CHECK NET agree to display their logos, description texts and related links in their respective websites. Additionally, **Rural BioReFarmeries** and NUTRI-CHECK NET shall provide bilaterally free dissemination of projects, events, information, and news from both parties through their websites, newsletters and social media.

3. Funding

The parties may jointly or independently mobilise resources for any activity, project, or program under this agreement. Prior to engaging in a collaborative activity, the parties shall stipulate the terms and conditions for the work to be performed as well as the financial arrangements of any such collaborative work through a separate written agreement. This agreement may also detail ownership of intellectual property rights and shall be signed and authorised by representatives of each party. The parties fully acknowledge that this agreement does not entail any funding obligation.

4. Monitoring and evaluation

The parties shall convene whenever necessary for consultation and further strategic collaboration. The consultation meetings shall serve to agree on and prepare an action plan for the successful implementation of activities necessary to meet the objectives of this agreement.

5. Intellectual property rights and publications

Both parties are responsible for providing the necessary technical elements for which they are the legal owner of graphic/image rights. For the activities that **Rural BioReFarmeries** and NUTRI-CHECK NET agree to organise together, both parties have the right to include each other's logos and promote them in their network. Any publication resulting from this collaboration shall reflect the joint efforts of both institutions. The employees or volunteers of **Rural BioReFarmeries** and NUTRI-CHECK NET shall not be entitled to any remuneration or other benefits respectively from **Rural BioReFarmeries** and NUTRI-CHECK NET.

6. Relationship

The parties shall always remain separate and independent entities. This non-binding and a non-exclusive agreement will in no way hinder the ability of either party to work with any other person, organisation, in whatever scope. Given the separate relationship, neither party shall hold itself as an agent of the other party, enter into any arrangement or transaction with third parties on behalf of the other nor in any way pledge or bind the credit of the other party.

7. Duration

This agreement shall become effective upon signature by the authorised officials from both parties and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by mutual consent. In the absence of mutual agreement by the authorised officials from both parties to extend the terms of this agreement, this agreement shall end on the 31st of March 2026, as **Rural BioReFarmeries** concludes its operations at that date.

On behalf of Rural BioReFarmeries

Ireland, XX/XX/2025

Niall Smith

Niall Smith (Nov 11, 2025 13:16:06 GMT)
Niall Smith, Head of Research

11/11/25

On behalf of NUTRI-CHECK NET

CHESHIRE, UK, 22/10/25

S. Kendall

Sarah Kendall, Scientific Co-ordinator